

responsive and high yielding, it is not popular with farmers. Most farmers in the region own small farms and grow glutinous rice yearly for family consumption. Few own enough land to grow RD9 for trade.

2. Northeast: RD5 and RD7 are high yielding, resistant to diseases and insects, and responsive to fertilizers. Selection of

the proper rice variety, planting date, seedbed location, and pest and disease control in the seedbed gave high production and other benefits.

3. Central: yellow orange leaf disease and brown planthopper are the major problems. Carbofuran (3%) applied once in the seedbed at the rate of 3 1.25 kg/ha was effective.

4. South: The pest and disease levels were comparable in plots planted to the government-recommended varieties (BKN 6402-352, NPY 132, and PN43) and to local varieties (LK and KMR). Yields were similar, but the recommended varieties were more profitable than the local ones. \mathbb{W}

Control of rice blast by tricyclazole 75W.P.

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On the first crop of 1977, the systemic fungicide Tricyclazole 75 W.P. was tested for control of rice blast on the variety Taiwan 5 in the field. Two popular rice blast fungicides, Hinosan 50 E.C. and Kitazin-p 48 E.C., were used as control.

Tricyclazole 75 W.P. was applied as a soil drench at the seedling stage 1 day before transplanting by machine. The second foliar application was made at 2 days before heading. The two other fungicides were applied twice as foliar application for leaf blast control and twice more for neck blast control.

Tricyclazole 75 W.P. at the rates of 2 and 3 g/flat as a soil drench and at 0.4 kg/ha as a foliar treatment provided excellent control of leaf and neck blast, similar to that by Hinosan (see table). \mathbb{W}

Control of rice blast by Tricyclazole 75 W.P.^a, Chia-yi, Taiwan.

Treatment	Rate of flat ^b application	foliar applications ^c (no.)		Disease incidence		Yield (t/ha)
		Leaf blast	Neck blast	Leaf blast (70)	Neck blast (%)	
Tricyclazole 15 W.P.	2 g/flat	0	1	11.4 ab	1.2 a	5.1 ab
Tricyclazole 15 W.P.	3 g/flat	0	1	11.5 ab	0.7 a	5.5 a
Hinosan 50 E.C.	0	2	2	8.4 a	2.0 a	5.2 a
Kitazin-p 48 E.C.	0	2	2	20.3 b	6.1 b	4.6 bc
Untreated control	0	0	0	34.5 c	16.4 c	4.2 c

^a Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level.

^b At 1 day before machine transplanting, suspending fungicide in 0.5 liter of water and pouring the suspension uniformly over the soil surface of 28day-old-rice plants growing in a 28- × 58- × 3-cm transplant flat.

^c By hand sprayer: once with tricyclazole (0.4 kg/ha) for neck blast control, twice with Hinosan (1 liter/ha) for leaf blast, and twice with Kitazin-p (1.2 liters/ha) for neck blast.

The effect of certain fungicides on rice sheath rot

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Ten fungicides were tested at 0.1 and 0.2% concentrations against

Acrocyndrium oryzae (since revised as *Sarocladium attenuatum*), the pathogen that causes sheath rot of rice.

Both concentrations of benomyl, carbendazim, edifenphos and mancozeb M45 inhibited the growth of *A. oryzae*, but the 0.2% level was much more effective. \mathbb{W}

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Recent brown planthopper incidence and its implications in Malaysia

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Until recently only sporadic and isolated infestations of planthoppers were observed in Malaysia, although damage was sometimes rather serious. The first incidence, recorded in 1925, was an outbreak of the whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* species in Krian (see table). Another outbreak occurred in late 1929 in Province Wellesley and Krian. Apparently no other major infestation was noted until 1967, when the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and *S. furcifera* seriously attacked and destroyed more than 6,000 ha of rice in Trengganu. Closely following that, hopperburn occurred in a number of rice-growing areas. Within the last few years, similar attacks were again reported, usually for the first time, over smaller and more isolated areas. However, no outbreaks occurred over large areas until 1977, when extensive rice fields in Tanjong Karang were attacked by the brown planthopper. Similar brown planthopper buildups, although much smaller in scale, also occurred in Perak (Langkap, Sungai Manek, Parit, and Krian), Malacca, Negri Sembilan, and Province Wellesley (see table).

The brown planthopper may soon become the major rice pest in Malaysia.

Some factors that favor its buildup are becoming more prevalent with improved cultivation practices. They include:

- 1) intensive cultivation of rice (e.g., double-cropping, triple-cropping, growing of 5 crops in 2 years);
- 2) large-scale planting of high yielding, high-tillering and nitrogen-responsive hopper-susceptible varieties such as Bahagia, Jaya, Mat Candu, and Seri Sekinchan;
- 3) close spacing between rice plants (e.g., 20 cm in parts of Sekinchan);
- 4) staggered or continuous cropping;

5) use of excessive fertilizers, particularly high rates of nitrogen; and 6) intensive and indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum insecticides.

Among the major researches currently undertaken are 1) more comprehensive studies of the biology and ecology of the planthopper under local conditions; 2) evaluation and screening for resistant varieties; 3) developing a surveillance and monitoring system to provide early detection so that appropriate and timely control measures

may be taken; 4) evaluation of intensive light trapping for control; 5) investigation of cultural aspects relating to planthopper development; 6) studies of the role and optimal employment of natural enemies; and 7) investigations of the efficient and judicious use of pesticides. ❧

Infestations of rice planthoppers observed or reported in Malaysia.

Year	Location	Planthopper	Remarks
1925	Perak (Krian)	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
1929	Perak (Krian)	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
	Province Wellesley	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
1967	Trengganu	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	More than 6,000 ha affected. Extensive and severe hopperburn
1968	Perlis	—	Hopperburn in small patches
	Kedah	—	”
	Perak	—	”
	Province Wellesley (Bukit Merah)	—	”
	Province Wellesley (Bumbong Lima)	—	”
1974	Province Wellesley (Sungai Sintok)	—	”
1975	Province Wellesley (Bumbong Lima)	<i>N. lugens</i> and <i>S. furcifera</i>	”
	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)		”
1976	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)		”
	Kedah (several localities)	—	”
	Negri Sembilan	—	”
	Selangor (Tanjong Karang)	—	”
1977	Selangor (Tanjong Karang)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Severe hopperburn in several localities. Affected area estimated to be more than 400 ha
1977	Malacca	—	General yellowing with heavy infestations
1977	Negri Sembilan	—	”
1917	Perak (Lankap)	<i>N. lugens</i>	”
1977	Perak (S. Manek, Parit, & Krian)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Heavy infestations
1977	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Hopperburn in small patches over an area of about 7 ha

Rapid reduction of brown planthoppers by intensive light trapping during an outbreak in Malaysia

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Light traps were observed to attract high populations of brown planthoppers (**BPH**) during a 1967 outbreak that affected about 6,000 ha of rice in Trengganu, Malaysia. Scientists then speculated that light traps might be used to control **BPH**. The **BPH** again showed strong phototropic response in a 1977 outbreak, in which about 15,000 ha was infested in Tanjong Karang. Depending on the natural infestations, as many as 92.16 million **BPH** (131 kg; 1 g = about 705 **BPH**) may be caught by 15 fluorescent lamp traps in 4% hours (1900–2330). Most insects were generally caught during the early evening hours. In one study, the catches per trap were 17,767 **BPH** from 1930 to 2030 hours, 1,531 from 2030 to 2130 hours, 4,389 from 2130 to 2230 hours, and 7,047 from 2230–2330 hours.

The enormous catches stimulated a study of the possibility of intensive light trapping to reduce **BPH** populations during an outbreak. In one study, 20 traps (using pressure gas lamps) were spaced around a 120-ha field from 1830 to 2300 hours. On 320 randomly selected hills (covering 32 sample points), the **BPH** population was reduced from 397 macropterous **BPH**/hill before light trapping to 156 macropterous **BPH**/hill after trapping (see table). In another study 47, 42, and 41 pressure lamp traps were used on 3 successive nights between 1900 and 2230 hours in a 100-ha field. Unlike in the earlier study, these traps were evenly spaced over the entire field.